

Supplementary Materials for
Systematic use of orthologous information to improve the
phylogeny of paralogous genes

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Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Table 1. Comparison between the ME and ML supertree and supermatrix topologies using the combination of all the alignment units for the 500 simulated datasets.

	Supermatrix more accurate than Supertree	Supertree more accurate than Supermatrix	Supermatrix equal to Supertree	Total
<i>ME</i>	235 (47.00%)	164 (32.80%)	101 (20.20%)	500
<i>ML</i>	215 (43.00%)	152 (30.40%)	133 (26.60%)	500

Supplementary Table 2. Percentage of branches with bootstrap support values higher than 70% and 95% on the Supermatrix-ME phylogenetic trees using only one alignment unit and the combination of all the alignment units for the 500 simulated datasets.

	BS > 70%	BS > 95%
<i>Supermatrix-ME Unit 1</i>	39%	10%
<i>Supermatrix-ME Unit 25</i>	48%	12%

Supplementary Table 3. Percentage of branches with bootstrap support values higher than 70% and 95% on the Supermatrix-ML phylogenetic trees using only one alignment unit and the combination of all the alignment units for the 500 simulated datasets.

	BS > 70%	BS > 95%
<i>Supermatrix-ML Unit 1</i>	45%	13%
<i>Supermatrix-ML Unit 25</i>	59%	17%

Supplementary Table 4. Comparison between the ME supertree and supermatrix topologies using the combination of all the alignment units and the Mouse-ML topology as reference for the 41 empirical datasets.

	Supermatrix more accurate than Supertree	Supertree more accurate than Supermatrix	Supermatrix equal to Supertree	Total
<i>ME</i>	25 (60.98%)	13 (31.71%)	3 (7.31%)	41

Supplementary Fig. 1 | Comparison between supertree and supermatrix phylogenetic trees using the combination of all the alignment units with the trees coming from only one alignment unit in the simulated datasets. Heatmap of relative normalised Robinson-Foulds (RF) distances per dataset among the supertree and supermatrix using the combination of all the alignment units and Unit 1 topologies with either ME (top) or ML (bottom). The relative normalised RF distances were computed by dividing the topology with the highest RF by the remaining two topologies. Both heatmap plots were ordered by the relative normalised RF distances of Unit 1 topologies.

Supplementary Fig. 2 | Confidence limits on the supermatrix phylogenies in the simulated datasets. Average bootstrap support values per added unit for the Supermatrix-ME (top) and Supermatrix-ML (bottom) topologies in the simulated datasets.

Supplementary Fig. 3 | Effect of the supertree and supermatrix topologies on each of the mouse empirical datasets. Robinson-Foulds distances per added alignment unit between the supertree and supermatrix distance-based topologies (Supertree-ME, Supermatrix-ME) without including mouse paralogs multiple sequence alignments and the RAxML trees computed only on the multiple sequence alignments of the mouse paralogs per family (ML-MOUSE).

Supplementary Fig. 4 | Comparison between supertree and supermatrix phylogenetic trees using the combination of all the alignment units with the ML trees coming from only the mouse multiple sequence alignment in the mouse empirical datasets. Heatmap of relative normalised Robinson-Foulds (RF) distances per dataset among the supertree and supermatrix using the combination of all the alignment units and Unit 1 topologies with ME. The relative normalised RF distances were computed by dividing the topology with the highest RF by the remaining two topologies. The heatmap plot was ordered by the relative normalised RF distances of Unit 1 topologies.